

Stoichiometry and Kinetic Studies of Oxidation of structurally related Organic Substrates, viz. Thiourea, *N*-Phenylthiourea and *N,N'*-Diphenylthiourea with Ammonium Hexanitrate-cerate(IV) in Perchloric Acid Medium

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In planning optimal analytical conditions through stoichiometry as well as in the study of structure-reactivity correlations of oxidation of thiourea (TU), *N*-phenylthiourea (*N*-PTU), *N,N'*-diphenylthiourea (*N,N'*-DPTU) with cerium(IV) in perchloric acid medium, systematic spectrophotometric kinetic studies at 295 nm are of paramount importance. Second order rate constants (k_2) obtained in these investigations are utilised to correlate the effects of variations of [thiourea or substituted thioureas], [cerium(IV)], $[H^+]$, $\mu = [ClO_4^-]$, [cerium(III)] and variation of temperature. The oxidation reactions of thiourea and *N*-phenyl thiourea (sym.) with cerium(IV) are essentially controlled by the substitution at the oxidant centre in an overall inner-sphere process. The reactive species, $(CeOH)^{3+}$ oxidises the protonated thioureas considerably more rapidly than Ce^{4+} . The mechanism of the oxidation reaction is that it takes place through the formation of a free radical intermediate due to the cleavage of a S-H bond (present in a monoprotonated species) followed by the conversion into the corresponding disulphide due to dimerisation. These disulphides undergo subsequent oxidation to the corresponding sulphones and finally to hydroxy compounds with the formation of H_2SO_4 and the corresponding oxygen analogues, e.g. urea, di(*p*-hydroxyphenyl)urea. Oxidation reaction rates, as well as thermodynamic parameters are correlated to the structure-reactivity of the aforementioned organic substrates. A suitable rate law in consonance with the experimental observations is also suggested.

Davies¹ studied the oxidation of thiourea and symmetrical alkylthioureas with Mn^{III} in perchloric acid medium and observed that the oxidation of these substrates takes place through the formation of S-S bonded products, in each case and finally concluded that the oxidation proceeds through an inner-sphere mechanism with substitution at Mn^{III} centre as the rate-determining process. Turkevich and Dmitrishin² carried out analytical estimations of thiourea and symmetrical phenylthioureas with cerium(IV) in sulphuric acid medium at 20° and separately at 50° for different intervals of time. However, these oxidations have not led to the complete oxidations of these substrates but determinations are based on some empirical factors indicating intermediate stages of oxidation. Spectrophotometric kinetics of oxidation of some

α -mercaptocarboxylic acids, thiourea and its *N*-substituted derivatives by cerium(IV) in sulphuric acid medium was undertaken by McAuley *et al.*^{3,4} and they have concluded that the kinetics of oxidation are consistent with a free radical formation, radical dimerisation and subsequent oxidation to the sulphones and further the reaction rates were compared with the reactions of the corresponding oxygen analogues. In acid solutions, thiourea and symmetrical phenylthiourea molecules are believed to be monoprotonated⁵. For example, the tautomeric forms of the monoprotonated *N,N'*-diphenyl thiourea species may be written as :

Thiourea and symmetrical alkylthioureas are converted into the corresponding disulphides in the analogous reactions with cerium(IV)⁶ and cobalt(III)⁷. Mahanti⁸ stated that the oxidation of sulphur compounds proceeds through a radical intermediate, e.g. C₆H₅S[•]. The greater stability of these S containing radicals was demonstrated by the experimental observations that α -mercapto acids yield a disulphide as an oxidation product³. McAuley and Shankar⁹ made a reinvestigation of the reaction of thiourea and its *N*-substituted derivatives with Co^{III} in aqueous perchlorate media over a temperature range 8–25° and at [H⁺] = 0.17–1.44 *M* using a stopped-flow apparatus. This work revealed that there was no evidence for intermediate complex formation and k_{obs} may be expressed in the form $k_{\text{obs}} = k_1(k_2K_f/[H^+])$, where k_1 and k_2 refer to the reactions involving Co³⁺(aq.) and [Co(OH)²⁺](aq.) reactive species respectively. Amjad and McAuley¹⁰ carried out the kinetics of oxidation of thiourea by V^{IV} in perchlorate media at 25° over the [H⁺] range 0.2–1.40 *M*, using a modified stopped-flow system. Several pathways were identified and the existence of 1 : 1 thiourea-V^{IV} intermediate complex was also proved. Lalani *et al.*¹¹ made a detailed study of the kinetics of oxidation of thiourea and substituted thioureas by hexacyanoferrate(III) in acid medium. It was believed that the oxidation reaction proceeds through an outer-sphere mechanism involving complex formation between protonated species of thiourea and [Fe(CN)₆]³⁺. The appropriate rate law in consonance with the above kinetic studies was also derived. Saradamba *et al.*¹² made detailed investigations into the kinetics of oxidation of thiourea by Fe(ClO₄)₃ in presence of 2,2'-bipyridyl under pseudo-first order conditions and the results indicated the reaction to be first order with respect to Fe^{III} and thiourea. Plots of 1/ k , vs 1/[H bipyridyl⁺] were linear with a positive intercept on 1/ k axis. The effect of dielectric constant using methanol was also studied. The calculated free energy of transfer of initial and transient state showed greater stabilisation of protonated thiourea and also inhibition of solvent methanol.

Stoichiometry : Stoichiometry of the reaction between the organic substrate, viz. TU, *N*-PTU

and *N,N'*-DPTU and cerium(IV) has been established for the experimental conditions employed as well as for 24, 48 and 72 h of reaction. In every case it was found that one mole of TU requires 8.0 equivalents of cerium(IV) for oxidation to urea stage, one mole of *N*-PTU requires 24.0 equivalents of cerium(IV) for oxidation to formic acid stage, one mole of *N,N'*-DPTU requires 40.0 equivalents of cerium(IV) for oxidation to formic acid stage. Further, it was found that the oxidation reaction upto the urea stage in the case of TU and *p*-benzoquinone stage in the case of *N*-PTU and *N,N'*-DPTU is fast and it completes within a few minutes. However, the final stage of oxidation, viz. formic acid requires more time. One of the oxidation products, viz. formic acid, in case of *N*-PTU and *N,N'*-DPTU is not further oxidised under the experimental conditions employed. It is also observed that the factor of stoichiometries of oxidation remained constant even with the change of stipulated reaction times.

The end-product, viz. urea formed in these oxidation reactions was tested through the biuret test. The other end-product, formic acid responded positively with (a) acidified KMnO₄ solution, (b) Fehling's solution and (c) Tollen's reagent¹³. One of the intermediate oxidation products, viz. *p*-hydroxyphenylurea in case of *N*-PTU and di(*p*-hydroxyphenyl)urea in case of *N,N'*-DPTU was tested with neutral FeCl₃¹³. Quinones formed as intermediate oxidation products were also tested after duly converting them into hydroquinones through reaction with Zn dust and a few drops of concentrated HCl followed by the test with neutral FeCl₃¹³. Free radical intermediates were also tested through acrylonitrile polymerisation in the absence of air. Sulphones¹⁴, which are formed as intermediate oxidation products, were also tested. The following patterns of oxidation are consistent with the observed stoichiometries.

(A) 1 Thiourea : 8.0 cerium(IV)

Fig. 1. Effect of variation of $[Ce^{IV}]$ on second order rate constant (k_2) in perchloric acid medium : (I) [TU] = $1.87 \times 10^{-4} M$ at 4° ; (II) [N-PTU] = $6.25 \times 10^{-5} M$ at 20° ; (III) [N,N'-DPTU] = $3.75 \times 10^{-5} M$ at 40° ; $[HClO_4] = 0.5$ and $2.0 M$.

Effect of $[H^+]$ concentration on rate constant :
The influence of variation of $[HClO_4]$ or $[H^+]$ was studied for the mixtures of $[HClO_4]$ and $[NaClO_4]$ giving $\mu = [ClO_4^-] = 4.0 M$. The results representing the relation between $1/k_{2(obs)}$ vs $[H^+]$ are shown in Fig. 2.

Fig. 2. Plots of reciprocal of k_2 vs $[H^+]$ in perchloric acid medium : explanation for (I), (II) and (III) same as in Fig. 1; $[Ce^{IV}] = 1.5 \times 10^{-3} M$, $[ClO_4^-] = 4.0 M$.

There was a continuous proportional decrease in the second order rate constant (k_2) as $[H^+]$ increases from 0.25 to $3.0 M$. The linear plots obtained in Fig. 2, i.e. $1/k_{2(obs)}$ vs $[H^+]$ are at $4 \pm 0.05^\circ$ for TU, while $20 \pm 0.05^\circ$ for N-PTU and N,N'-DPTU. A meticulous analysis of Fig. 2 shows that the rates are lower at higher acidities much more than anticipated, e.g. in the case of TU at $[H^+] = 0.5 M$, $k_2 = 4.122 \times 10^{-4} dm^3 mol^{-1} s^{-1}$ while at $[H^+] = 3.0 M$, $k_2 = 1.185 \times 10^{-4} dm^3 mol^{-1} s^{-1}$. The possible mechanism taking into account the effect of $[H^+]$ and protonation of TU and also hydrolysis of Ce^{IV} may be written as follows.

Mechanism : The following mechanism is consistent with the experimental observations.

In these equations T and TH^+ are unprotonated and monoprotonated thiourea molecules $(NH_2-C(=S)-NH_2)$ and $(^+NH_3-C(=S)-NH_2)$ or $(NH_2-C(=S)-NH_2)$, X is the radical produced $(NH=C-NH_2)$ by oxidation

(state of protonation is not known) and X_2 is a disulphide product formed in the rapid dimerisation reaction.

For this mechanism, the empirical rate law may be written as

$$-\frac{d[\text{Ce}^{\text{IV}}]}{dt} = K_{\text{obs}}[\text{Ce}^{\text{IV}}] [\text{Thiourea}] \quad (8)$$

However, incorporating the above equations, the rate law can be rewritten as

$$k_{2(\text{obs})} = \frac{k_1 [\text{H}^+] + k_2 K_h + k_3 K_a + k_4 K_a K_h / [\text{H}^+]}{([\text{H}^+] + K_h) (1 + K_a / [\text{H}^+])} \quad (9)$$

Two limiting cases of this equation will be of interest since they have also been observed in some reactions of manganese(III)¹⁵ :

a) If $K_a (k_3 + k_4 K_h / [\text{H}^+]) \ll k_1 [\text{H}^+] k_2 K_h$ and $1 \gg K_a / [\text{H}^+]$ then

$$k_{2(\text{obs})} = \frac{k_1 [\text{H}^+] + k_2 K_h}{[\text{H}^+] + K_h} \quad (10)$$

and

$$k_{\text{obs}} ([\text{H}^+] + K_h) = k_1 [\text{H}^+] + k_2 K_h \quad (11)$$

b) If $k_2 K_h \gg K_1 [\text{H}^+]$ in equation (10), then

$$k_{2(\text{obs})} = \frac{K_2 K_h}{[\text{H}^+] + K_h}$$

$$\text{and } \frac{1}{k_{2(\text{obs})}} = \frac{[\text{H}^+]}{k_2 K_h} + \frac{1}{K_2} \quad (12)$$

The above assumptions are found valid under the experimental conditions employed for these kinetic studies. For this mechanism, the establishment of limiting forms (10) and (11) at any particular temperature is seen to be largely dependent on the magnitude of K_a which is only available for thiourea ($K_a \approx 10^{-2}$, 1 M at 25°)⁵. However, with this order of magnitude for K_a , implicit assumption is obviously that the rate constants k_3 and k_4 are not very much larger than k_1 and k_2 although, of course, they could be of similar magnitude or even smaller.

Since the decomposition of thiourea by perchloric acid is too slow to account for these deviations and kinetic medium effects of this magnitude seen very unlikely, it is reasonable to suppose that further protonation of thioureas occurs at high acidity, producing species which react

at lower rates with cerium(IV). According to equation (10), the slopes and intercepts of the linear plots of Fig. 2 give k_1 and $k_2 K_h$ respectively, for different thioureas and therefore K_h values are calculated at different temperatures ($K_h = 0.6345$ at $4 \pm 0.05^\circ$ while $K_h = 0.833$ at $20 \pm 0.05^\circ$).

At the lowest experimental acid concentration, $[\text{H}^+] = 0.5$ M in equation (9) then with $K_a = 10^{-2}$ at 1 M and at 25° and $K_h = 0.81$ at 1 M, it follows that $k_4 \ll 4 \times 10^5 \text{ M}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$ at 25°. It has been found in a number of faster reactions of cobalt(III)¹⁶ and manganese(III) that $k_3 \leq k_4$ in steps corresponding to equations (5) and (6). Thus it is likely that $k_3 \leq 4 \times 10^5 \text{ M}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$ at 25° justifying the assumption that intercepts of plots of equation (12) for the data for thioureas are essentially $k_2 K_h$ as substantiated by linear Arrhenius plots for these parameters.

Variation of rate constant with ionic strength :

A series of kinetic runs were carried out keeping the initial concentrations of $[\text{Ce}^{\text{IV}}]$ and TU/N-PTU/N,N'-DPTU stoichiometrically equivalent and $[\text{H}^+] = 0.5$ M. However, the temperatures employed were $4 \pm 0.05^\circ$ for TU while $20 \pm 0.05^\circ$ for N-PTU and N,N'-DPTU. The effect of ionic strength ($\mu = [\text{ClO}_4^-]$) was studied in the range

Fig. 3 Plots of $\log k/k_0$ vs $\sqrt{\mu}$ in perchloric acid medium explanation for (I), (II) and (III) same as in Fig 1, $[\text{Ce}^{\text{IV}}] = 1.5 \times 10^{-3}$ M, $[\text{HClO}_4] = 0.5$ M

2.0–4.0 M by adding requisite amounts of NaClO₄ and simultaneously maintaining [H⁺] constant (0.5 M) with the help of HClO₄. A relation, log k/k_0 vs $\sqrt{\mu}$ is graphically represented in Fig. 3 (where k = rate constant at different ionic strengths and k_0 = rate constant without maintaining ionic strength). A linear plot with a higher positive slope is obtained in the study of this relationship indicating the involvement of an ion-ion interaction¹⁷.

Variation of rate constant with Ce^{III} : A series of kinetic runs were carried out keeping the initial concentration of cerium(IV), TU/*N*-PTU/*N,N'*-DPTU stoichiometrically equivalent at [H⁺] = 0.5 M and [NaClO₄] = 2.0 M. However, the temperatures employed were 4 ± 0.05° for TU while 20 ± 0.05° for *N*-PTU and *N,N'*-DPTU. The effect of variation of added [Ce^{III}] was studied

Fig. 4. Effect of variation of added [Ce^{III}] on k_2 in perchloric acid medium : explanation for (I), (II) and (III) same as in Fig. 1; [Ce^{IV}] = 1.5 × 10⁻³ M, [HClO₄] = 0.5 M, [NaClO₄] = 2.0 M.

in the range 1.5 × 10⁻³ to 12.0 × 10⁻³ M, by adding requisite amounts of cerium(III) nitrate prepared in 1 M perchloric acid medium. The variation of second order rate constant (k_2) thus obtained with respect to each substrate is graphically presented in Fig. 4. It is also observed from Fig. 4 that cerium(III) has a marginal retardation effect on the second order rate constant (k_2) for an increase of cerium(III) concentration

from 1.5 × 10⁻³ to 4.5 × 10⁻³ M. However, the rate of oxidation rapidly decreases at higher concentrations of cerium(III), i.e. 12.0 × 10⁻³ M. Perhaps this type of marginal decrease in the rate of oxidation with the gradual increase of added [Ce^{III}] may be due to (i) the association of cerium(IV) or reactive cerium(IV) species with the added cerium(III) and (ii) the complex formation between cerium(III) and thioureas, viz. TU, *N*-PTU, *N,N'*-DPTU as cerium(III) is known to form such complexes with these organic substrates. Such a complex formation between cerium(III) and the thioureas would effectively reduce the substrate concentration, i.e. [TU] or [*N*-PTU] or [*N,N'*-DPTU] in the reaction medium with due lapse of time. Yost *et al.*¹⁸ and Blaustein and Gryder¹⁹ have already established such instances of association of cerium(IV) with the added cerium(III) through ion-migration experiments. In spite of these obvious reasons, it is difficult to explain the abnormal retardation effect of cerium(III) for there is a lack of any mathematical correlation between the observed retardation in rate constant (k_2) with the variation of added cerium(III).

Thermodynamic parameters : Second order rate constant (k_2) for the reaction employing stoichiometrically equivalent concentrations of [TU] = 1.87 × 10⁻⁴ M or [*N*-PTU] = 6.25 × 10⁻⁵ M or [*N,N'*-DPTU] = 3.75 × 10⁻⁵ M and [Ce^{IV}] = 1.5 × 10⁻³ M at [H⁺] = 0.5 M and μ = [ClO₄⁻] = 2.0 M were determined at different temperatures. The rate constants (k_2) obtained at different temperatures and the evaluated thermodynamic parameters are furnished in Tables 1 and 2.

TABLE 1—VARIATION OF RATE CONSTANT WITH TEMPERATURE

Thiourea :						
Temp. (K)	277.0	281.0	285.0	289.0	293.0	
$k_2 \times 10^4 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$	1.676	2.091	2.378	3.04	3.523	
<i>N</i> -Phenylthiourea :						
Temp. (K)	285.0	289.0	293.0	298.0	303.0	308.0
$k_2 \times 10^4 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$	0.7514	1.041	1.608	2.113	3.661	5.657
<i>N,N'</i> -Diphenylthiourea :						
Temp. (K)	285.0	289.0	293.0	298.0	303.0	308.0
$k_2 \times 10^4 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$	0.393	0.566	1.041	1.549	2.47	3.823

Results and Discussion

The above results show that the order of reaction between TU or *N*-PTU or *N,N'*-DPTU and cerium(IV) in perchloric acid medium is unity with respect to each reactant. Thioureas employed in these oxidation reactions are the *N*-phenylthiourea and *N,N'*-diphenylthiourea which are symmetrical diphenyl derivatives. In each case, a first order dependence of the rate on the concentrations of both oxidant and thiourea is consistent with negligible stoichiometric concentrations of complexes between the reactants and lack of tautomeric kinetic control²⁰ such as that in the following equilibria.

The data are thus consistent with the very rapid establishment of proton equilibria, such as equations (1) and (2) and tautomeric equilibria like above, if the thioureas actually exist in enol or keto forms in solutions^{21,22}.

TABLE 2—THERMODYNAMIC PARAMETERS (293 K)

Substrate	ΔE^\ddagger kJ mol ⁻¹	$-\Delta H^\ddagger$ kJ mol ⁻¹	ΔS^\ddagger JK ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹	ΔG^\ddagger kJ mol ⁻¹	<i>A</i> s ⁻¹
Thiourea	32.95	28.07	-0.19	-83.39	2.614×10^2
<i>N</i> -Phenylthiourea	63.75	58.87	-0.077	-81.48	3.667×10^7
<i>NN'</i> -Diphenylthiourea	73.82	68.95	-0.039	-80.43	1.481×10^9

As discussed earlier, in the effect of [H⁺] on rate constant, the assignment of complete mechanism through equations such as (9) requires a knowledge of *K_a*, which has only been estimated for the parent thiourea molecule. In any event, derived rate constant will refer to reactions of either or both tautomers as mentioned in the above equilibrium. A knowledge of the magnitude of *K_a* for thiourea itself⁵ and observation of equation (9) accounts reasonably well for the kinetic data for reactions of this species suggest that the rate parameters for thiourea may be used as a basis for the discussion of the reaction of symmetrical phenyl derivatives.

The rate constants for these reactions of Ce⁴⁺(aq.) and CeOH³⁺(aq.) with monoprotonated thiourea are just similar to those of complexation of cerium(IV) or manganese(III) by neutral HF²³ and to the rate constants for their redox reactions with neutral H₂O₂, HNO₂ or hydroquinone. In addition, the upper limits of rate constants for reactions of Ce⁴⁺(aq.) and CeOH³⁺(aq.) with unprotonated thiourea molecules (and presumably the unprotonated phenyl thioureas) are evidently not too different from those for the monoprotonated species. The small range of rate constants for reactions of CeOH³⁺(aq.) with the monoprotonated thioureas is analogous to that found in the corresponding substitution-controlled redox reactions of CoOH²⁺(aq.)^{7,16} and contrasts sharply with the much larger range of rates with cerium(IV) as oxidant in 0.5 *M* sulphuric acid⁶. These observations indicate that the reactions of thiourea and phenylthioureas (symmetrical) with Ce^{IV} are essentially controlled by the substitution at the oxidant centre in an overall inner-sphere process^{15,16}.

Thus if *k_{el}* is greater than *k₋₀* in the above scheme, then *K_{obs}* = *K_ok₀* and the rate will be limited by the rate of conversion of the ion-pair [Ce⁴⁺, T] into the inner-sphere complex [Ce⁴⁺, T]. A substitution-controlled model extends to the observed activation parameters, e.g.

$$\Delta H_{\text{obs}}^\ddagger = \Delta H_o^\ddagger + \Delta H_o$$

where ΔH_o^\ddagger and ΔH_o are the enthalpies of activation and ion association respectively. Although the application of a simple electrostatic model^{24,25} for estimation of the parameters of ion association is certainly open to question at high ionic strengths, the results for substitution-controlled reactions of CoOH²⁺(aq.) at ionic strength 3 *M* are reasonably consistent with its predictions²⁶. Similar rate constants at 4° as well as at 20° for reactions of CeOH³⁺(aq.) with the employed thiourea and phenylthioureas are the result of small compen-

sating enthalpic and entropic variations which are evidently related to the properties of the reductant in the overall complexation process. Solvational changes in an aqueous medium are likely to be cooperative in both ion-pair formation and activation and these may be the source of the observed effects. Inspection of the activation parameters of substitution controlled $\text{CoOH}^{2+}(\text{aq.})$ reaction^{16,26} suggested that small or slightly negative entropies of activation might be expected in the analogous reactions of $\text{CeOH}^{3+}(\text{aq.})$ with monoprotonated thiourea molecules. Similar observations are also made with $\text{MnOH}^{2+}(\text{aq.})$ as reactive species¹.

Another indication that the rate parameters are sensitive to the formal charge on the reductant is provided by the observation of complicated acid dependence in the reactions with thioureas.

With increase of $[\text{H}^+]$, there is a possibility of increasing protonation and evidently leads to decrease in rate where rate of reaction with unprotonated reductant species appears to be lower than that monoprotonated form. Both charge and steric effects are obviously important in determining the rate of substitution at cerium(IV) centre, and further these symmetrical thioureas with free terminal 'N' atom if coordination through unprotonated nitrogen atoms is the rate-determining process. However, phenylation of 'N' atom in Tu has such a marked effect on the rates of oxidation with $\text{Ce}^{4+}(\text{aq.})$ that only upper limits of rate constant may be derived. Coordination through nitrogen atoms is evidently important in both the TU series and in the corresponding reactions of monoprotonated hydrazines²⁷ where the reaction of $\text{MnOH}^{2+}(\text{aq.})$ is also the only detectable reaction pathway.

The smaller kinetic effects of blocking of the nitrogen atoms in thioureas as compared to the large general rate decrease observed with hydrazines may be due to preferred attachment of $\text{CeOH}^{3+}(\text{aq.})$ at the sulphur atom of the enol form of the reductant. According to the available experimental evidence in many of the features expected of a substitution controlled inner-sphere process rather than an outer-sphere mechanism. Further, in these oxidations there is a contribution

to the heat term from the dimerisation of free radical. Using the $-\text{S}-\text{S}-$ bond dissociation energy as $-54 \text{ kcal mol}^{-1}$ ²⁸, the enthalpy change for the radical formation ($\Delta H_{\text{rad}}^{\circ}$) according to the equation,

may be calculated. There is a progressive change in the overall values of entropy as well as enthalpies of activation and free energy decrease. These variations reflect the following relationship of the reactivity sequence : thiourea > *N*-phenylthiourea > *N,N'*-diphenylthiourea. This is also in accordance with the order of inductive effects found earlier^{29,30}. Since the reaction involves the transfer of electrons from the organic substrate to the metal ion, any group which has the tendency to increase the electron density at the point of transfer is likely to enhance the rate or obviously decrease the rate with the groups which have a tendency to decrease the electron density.

Experimental

In general, the materials employed were of highest purity available (AnalaR; E. Merck, G.R.) unless otherwise specified.

A 0.1 *M* solution of cerium(IV) in 1.0 *M* perchloric acid was prepared by dissolving ceric ammonium nitrate in 1.0 *M* perchloric acid prepared with conductivity water. The cerium(IV) solution was standardised with a standard iron(II) solution to a potentiometric end-point and separately by a visual titration using ferroin as an indicator.

Perchloric acid was proportionately diluted with conductivity water to the desired strength. A 0.01 *M* solution of each of thiourea and *N*-phenylthiourea was prepared in conductivity water, and *N,N'*-DPTU in glacial acetic acid as it is sparingly soluble in water. To ensure the purity of these organic substrates was checked by an iodometric method³¹ and found to be as per the AnalaR specifications.

Kinetic procedure : Requisite volumes of cerium(IV) solution and all other reagents (except

organic substrate), viz. perchloric acid and sodium perchlorate, were taken in a pyrex glass bottle, and separately the respective organic substrate solution (TU or *N*-PTU or *N,N'*-DPTU) was placed in another pyrex bottle. The bottles were then placed in a thermostat (INSREF) at 4° or 20 ± 0.05°. After temperature equilibration, requisite volumes of organic substrate as well as cerium(IV) solution with all other addenda were rapidly sucked into a 1 cm quartz cell which was already kept in the cell compartment of a Shimadzu UV 240 spectrophotometer. The cell compartments were also thermostated at the above temperatures and the wavelength was maintained at 295 nm. This wavelength was so chosen because the absorption spectrum of cerium(IV) in perchloric acid is characterised by a single broad absorption band in the ultraviolet range. The shape of the band and its comparatively high intensity indicate that it is a charge-transfer band. The small difference in the position of the absorption maximum is only in 5.95 *M* perchloric acid (34 000 cm⁻¹). Formation of complexes is not usually observed in perchloric acid medium and also under the set conditions of [H⁺] and [ClO₄⁻] employed in this kinetic work. The outer-sphere ligand naturally influences the position of absorption band maximum but only to a small extent.

The changes in optical densities were observed at 295 nm and the peak has been attributed conclusively to cerium(IV) only. There was no contribution in this region from either the thioureas or the reaction products or cerium(III) formed during the course of the reaction. In all cases, the ionic strength was 2.0 *M*. Indeed this type of measuring the reaction rate is usually referred to as stopped-flow technique. The spectrophotometric kinetic runs were followed for only 0.3–0.7 of the life-time of the reaction so that the observed second order rate data would not be influenced by any sequential reactions. During the course of the spectrophotometric kinetic work the reference solution used in reference cell normally contained [H⁺] = 0.5 *M* and μ = [ClO₄⁻] = 2.0 *M*. Each value of *k*_{2(obs)} is the result of at least three replicate kinetic runs. The agreement between the replicate runs was within ± 3%.

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